

Chemistry of the Seeds of *Angelica archangelica* Linn.

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In addition to umbelliprenin, isoimperatorin, bergapten, prangolarin, β -sitosterol and ostruthol, a glycol has been isolated from the seeds of *Angelica archangelica*. From degradative experiments the glycol has been identified as oxypeucedanin hydrate.

The recent isolation of two new compounds from our laboratory^{1,2} from the root of *Angelica archangelica* Linn. prompted us to reinvestigate the seeds of the same plant, investigation on which is also being pursued by other group of workers^{3,4}. The material for this purpose was collected from Kashmir.

The petroleum (b.p. 60-80°) extract of the dry powdered seeds of *A. archangelica* after concentration and cooling gave a solid (A). The mother liquor was then chromatographed over Brockmann alumina. Petroleum (b.p. 40-60°) eluted fractions upon evaporation gave thick oil which crystallised from aqueous methanol in fine needles, $C_{14}H_{20}O_3$, m.p. 61°. The spectral data: λ_{max}^{Nujol} 5.8 (lactone) and 8.88 μ (ether), λ_{max}^{EtOH} 323 m μ (log ϵ 3.99) clearly demonstrated the presence of 7-oxygenated coumarin moiety with ether linkage in the compound. Final confirmation was made by hydrolysing the coumarin with acetic acid and sulphuric acid, when a phenolic compound, $C_9H_6O_3$, was obtained which crystallised from acetone in needles, m.p. 220-21°, identical with umbelliferone. High vacuum sublimation of the compound also furnished umbelliferone. The pyrolysis (high vacuum sublimation) of coumarin and its hydrolysis with the expulsion of C_{15} -unit with the formation of umbelliferone recalls the behaviour of preoxy coumarins and immediately suggests that the compound in all probability is umbelliprenin. It was subsequently confirmed by mixed m.p. determination and superimposable IR spectra.

The light petroleum and petroleum mixture (4:1) eluates of the chromatogram gave a solid, $C_{16}H_{14}O_4$, crystallising from benzene and petrol mixture in needles, m.p. 109-10°, λ_{max}^{Nujol} 5.8 (lactone); 8.9 (ether) and 9.3 μ (benzofuran); λ_{max}^{EtOH} 222, 240, 267 and 310 m μ (log ϵ , 4.30, 4.26, 4.20 and 4.13) was found to be a furocoumarin. Identity of this with isoimperatorin was established by degradative experiment. Acid hydrolysis of the substance gave a phenolic furocoumarin with the elimination of a C_2 -unit. The phenolic constituent upon treatment with diazomethane yielded a solid, $C_{12}H_8O_4$, m.p. 189-90° characterised as bergapten.

The coumarin, $C_{11}H_8O_4$, obtained from the petroleum and benzene mixture (19:1)

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2. Sen Gupta, (Miss) S., D. Phil. (Sc.) thesis, Calcutta University 1965.
3. Saino, T. O., *J. Pharm. Sci.*, 1964, **53**, 231.
4. Dwan, F. N., *Fortschr. Chem. Org. Naturstoffe*, 1952, **9**, 225.

eluates of the column crystallised from methanol in needles, m.p. 188-89°, found to be identical with bergapten.

The column upon further washing with petroleum and benzene mixture (4:1) followed by evaporation of the washings furnished another coumarin, $C_{16}H_{14}O_3$, which crystallised from ethyl acetate and petrol mixture in needles, m.p. 104-5°, (M^+286), $[\alpha]_D^{22} +22^\circ$ (in $CHCl_3$); λ_{max}^{Nol} 5.75 (lactone); 8.85 (ether) and 9.32 μ (benzofuran); λ_{max}^{EtOH} 223, 249, 266 and 309 $m\mu$ (log ϵ , 4.40, 4.27, 4.12 and 4.12) was found to be a furanocoumarin ether. Acid hydrolysis of this compound gave an alkali soluble solid which upon methylation gave a compound, $C_{16}H_{14}O_4$, m.p. 190-91°, found to be identical with bergapten. Final identity of the original compound with prangolarin was secured from an examination of their mixed m.p., and of their UV and IR spectra.

A solid, $C_{28}H_{50}O$, crystallised from chloroform and methanol mixture in needles, m.p. 135-36°, $[\alpha]_D^{25} -34^\circ$ (in $CHCl_3$), migrated out in the benzene eluate of the chromatogram. It responded to the Libermann-Burchard reaction for sterols. The sterol was finally identified as β -sitosterol.

Benzene and chloroform mixture (19:1) eluate of the column gave a solid $C_{21}H_{22}O_7$, crystallising from benzene and petrol mixture in needles, m.p. 137-38°, $[\alpha]_D^{25} -11^\circ$ (in pyridine). The ultraviolet λ_{max}^{EtOH} 220, 250 and 312 $m\mu$ (log ϵ , 4.45, 4.27 and 4.13) and infrared λ_{max}^{Nol} 2.8 (hydroxyl), 5.84 (lactone), 8.2 (ether) and 9.35 μ (benzofuran) spectra of the compound indicated the presence of a furano-coumarin moiety in the compound. Acetylation of the coumarin yielded an acetyl derivative, $C_{23}H_{24}O_8$, m.p. 128°, which lacked the hydroxyl peak in its IR spectrum. Alkali hydrolysis of the compound yielded tiglic acid, $C_9H_{16}O_2$, m.p. 63-64° and a diol, $C_{16}H_{18}O_6$. The latter crystallised from ethyl acetate in needles, m.p. 132°, found to be identical with oxypeucedanin hydrate. Acid hydrolysis of the coumarin gave a phenolic compound, $C_{11}H_6O_4$, m.p. 278-80°, identified as bergaptol. Thus the original compound, m.p. 137-38°, was established as ostruthol.

The chloroform washings of the column gave another solid, $C_{16}H_{16}O_6$ (M^+304), m.p. 129-30°, $[\alpha]_D^{25} -5^\circ$ (in pyridine) which was also found to be furano coumarin as evidenced from the IR: 2.85 (hydroxyl), 5.8 (lactone), 8.94 (ether) and 9.3 μ (benzofuran) and UV: λ_{max}^{EtOH} 224, 251, 259, 266 and 306 $m\mu$ (log ϵ , 4.40, 4.30, 4.26, 4.24, 4.17) data. The IR spectrum of the diacetate, $C_{20}H_{20}O_8$, m.p. 133-34°, lacked the hydroxyl peak discernible in the original compound. All these data proved the identity of the compound with oxypeucedanin hydrate.

The solid (A) which showed two spots in TLC upon chromatographic resolution furnished two compounds, one $C_{16}H_{14}O_4$, crystallising from benzene and petroleum mixture in needles, m.p. 109° and the other $C_{16}H_{14}O_4$ also from benzene and petroleum mixture in needles, m.p. 104°, $[\alpha]_D^{25} +20^\circ$ (in $CHCl_3$). The former was proved to be identical with iso-imperatorin and the latter as prangolarin from mixed m.p. determination comparison of IR spectra.

Chloroform extract of the defatted seeds gave two distinct spots in the TLC followed by a trailing; finally chromatographic resolution of the concentrated extract over acid-washed alumina followed by elution with solvents of increased polarity led to the isolation of prangolarin, iso-imperatorin, oxypeucedanin hydrate and β -sitosterol. All

these compounds were characterised by mixed m.p. determinations and other usual procedure.

EXPERIMENTAL

Dried and powdered seeds (400 gm.) of *A. archangelica* were extracted with petroleum (b.p. 60-80°) in a soxhlet for 30 hr. The oily concentrate (70 ml.) obtained after the removal of petrol was kept in the frigidaire when solid (A) deposited (7 gm.). The mother liquor left after the removal of the solid was chromatographed over acid-washed Brookmann alumina (400 gm.).

Isolation of Umbelliprenin.—The chromatogram upon elution with light petroleum (b.p. 40-60°) furnished a thick oily substance (yield, 0.15%) which was crystallised from aqueous methanol in fine needles, m.p. 61° (Found: C, 78.47; H, 8.58. Calc. for $C_{24}H_{20}O_3$: C, 78.70; H, 8.20%), found to be identical with umbelliprenin. The hydrolysed product (75 mg.) of the coumarin (400 mg), acetic acid (20 ml) and conc. H_2SO_4 (2 drops) was found to be a phenolic compound, crystallising from acetone in needles, m.p. 220-21° proved to be identical with umbelliferone. (Found: C, 66.95; H, 3.85. Calc. for $C_9H_6O_3$: C, 66.68; H, 3.71%). Even the original coumarin upon vacuum distillation furnished umbelliferone characteristic for the geraneloxy coumarins.

Isolation of Isoimperatorin.—Elution of the column with light petroleum and petroleum mixture (4:1) followed by evaporation of the eluates furnished a solid (yield, 0.2%), crystallising from benzene and petroleum mixture in thick rods, m.p. 109-10° (Found: C, 71.57; H, 5.35. Calc. for $C_{16}H_{14}O_4$: C, 71.10; H, 5.18%), found to be identical with isoimperatorin. The coumarin (400 mg) upon hydrolysing with acetic acid (20 ml) and conc. H_2SO_4 (2 drops) followed by working up the reaction product and methylation gave a solid, (110 mg), m.p. 189-90° identified as bargapten. (Found: 66.89; H, 3.95. Calc. for $C_{15}H_8O_4$: C, 66.68; H, 3.71%).

Isolation of Bargapten.—Washing the column with petrol and benzene mixture (10:1) followed by evaporation of the washings furnished a coumarin (yield, 0.025%), crystallising from methanol in needles, m.p. 188-89° identified as bargapten by comparing with an authentic sample. (Found: C, 66.92; H, 3.80. Calc. for $C_{15}H_8O_4$: C, 66.68; H, 3.71%).

Isolation of Prangolarin.—The 100 ml. fractions of the petroleum and benzene mixture (4:1) eluates of the chromatogram upon evaporation furnished a coumarin (yield, 0.2%), crystallising from ethyl acetate and petroleum mixture in needles, m.p. 104-5°, $[\alpha]_D^{22} + 22^\circ$ (in $CHCl_3$), (Found: C, 67.33; H, 4.87. Calc. for $C_{16}H_{14}O_3$: C, 67.14; H, 4.89%). The coumarin was proved to be identical with prangolarin. Hydrolysis of the coumarin (400 mg) with acetic acid (20 ml) and sulphuric acid (2 drops) followed by methylation of the reaction product with diazomethane furnished a solid (110 mg) crystallising from methanol in needles, m.p. 190-91° characterised as bargapten. (Found: C, 66.54; H, 3.75. Calc. for $C_{15}H_8O_4$: C, 66.68; H, 3.71%).

Isolation of β -Sitosterol.—Evaporation of the benzene eluate of the chromatogram furnished a sterol (yield, 0.025%), crystallised from chloroform and methanol mixture in needles, m.p. 135-36°, $[\alpha]_D - 34^\circ$ (in $CHCl_3$), (Found: C, 84.18; H, 12.52. Calc. for

$C_{29}H_{50}O$: C, 83.99; H, 12.16%). The sterol was identified as β -sitosterol by mixed melting point determination with an authentic sample.

Isolation of Ostruthol.—The chromatogram upon further elution with benzene and chloroform mixture (19:1) followed by evaporation of the eluate furnished a coumarin (yield, 0.15%) which was crystallised from benzene and petroleum mixture in needles, m.p. 137-38°, $[\alpha]_D^{25} -11^\circ$ (in pyridine), (Found: C, 65.40; H, 5.55. Calc. for $C_{11}H_{10}O_7$: C, 65.28; H, 5.70%). The coumarin (200 mg) upon acetylation with acetic anhydride (3 ml.) and pyridine (0.5 ml.) gave the acetyl derivative, crystallised from petrol and chloroform mixture in needles (yield, 200 mg), m.p. 128° (Found: C, 64.60; H, 5.85. Calc. for $C_{13}H_{14}O_8$: C, 64.48; H, 5.60%). Hydrolysis of the coumarin (400 mg) with aqueous ethanolic (8%) alkali (4 ml.) after working up in the usual procedure gave an acid (50 mg), m.p. 63-64°, (Found: C, 59.80; H, 8.20. Calc. for $C_5H_8O_6$: C, 60.00; H, 8.00%) identified as tiglic acid and a glycerol (150 mg), crystallised from ethyl acetate in needles, m.p. 132° (Found: C, 63.00; H, 5.30. Calc. for $C_{16}H_{18}O_6$: C, 63.15; H, 5.26%), found to be identical with oxypeucedanin hydrate. Acid hydrolysis of the coumarin (300 mg) with acetic acid (15 ml.) and conc. H_2SO_4 (4 drops) followed by working up the reaction product in the usual way furnished a phenolic solid (75 mg.) crystallising from methanol in needles, m.p. 278-80° (Found: C, 65.28; H, 2.75. Calc. for $C_{11}H_6O_4$: C, 65.34; H, 2.97%) which was identified as bergaptol.

Isolation of Oxypeucedanin Hydrate.—Chloroform washing of the Tswet column upon evaporation furnished a solid crystallising from ethyl acetate in needles, m.p. 129-30°, $[\alpha]_D^{25} -5^\circ$ (in pyridine) (yield, 0.01%), (Found: C, 63.30; H, 5.45. Calc. for $C_{16}H_{18}O_6$: C, 63.15; H, 5.26%), was proved to be identical with oxypeucedanin hydrate. The coumarin (150 mg) upon acetylation with acetic anhydride (3 ml) and pyridine (6 drops) followed by working up furnished the acetate crystallised from petrol in needles (150 mg), m.p. 133-34°, (Found: C, 61.60; H, 5.40. Calc. for $C_{18}H_{20}O_8$: C, 61.85; H, 5.15%), proved to be identical with oxypeucedanin diacetate.

Resolution of the crude Solid (A).—The solid (3 gm.) found to be a mixture of two coumarins indicated by the appearance of two spots in TLC was chromatographed over deactivated Brockmann alumina (300 gm). The chromatogram was then successively eluted with solvents of increasing polarity. Fractions of light petroleum (b.p. 40-60°) and petroleum (b.p. 60-80°) mixture (4:1) upon evaporation furnished a coumarin, m.p. 109° (yield 20%), while another coumarin, m.p. 104° (yield, 8%) was obtained by evaporating the petroleum and benzene mixture (4:1) eluate.

The coumarin, m.p. 109°, crystallised from benzene and petroleum mixture in thick rods (Found: C, 70.70; H, 5.20. Calc. for $C_{16}H_{14}O_4$: C, 71.10; H, 5.16%), was proved to be identical with isoperatorin from mixed melting point determination with an authentic sample.

The second coumarin, m.p. 104°, $[\alpha]_D^{25} +20^\circ$ (in $CHCl_3$), crystallising from benzene and petroleum mixture in needles (Found: C, 67.30; H, 5.10. Calc. for $C_{16}H_{14}O_3$: C, 67.14; H, 4.89%) was identified as prangolarin from mixed melting point determination.

Resolution of the Chloroform Extract.—The concentrated chloroform extract of the marc in the TLC showed two distinct spots for coumarin and also slight trailing. Chroma-

tographic resolution of the extract led to the isolation of prangolarin (yield, 0.01%), isomperatorin (yield, 0.012%), oxypoucedanin hydrate (yield, 0.005%) and β -sitosterol (yield, 0.02%).

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